

Antipyretic Activity-A Review

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Abstract

Human beings suffer from many ailments some common and some uncommon. Some ailments last for a short duration while others last for a longer time, one such medical condition is fever. Though fever is taken lightly not all fevers are easily recoverable. Depending on the severity of the medical condition the patient might require rest or might need medical help. In the present publication, the main focus is to study in detail various aspects of antipyretic activity.

Keywords

Antipyretic activity, Pyresis, Fever, Herbal medication, Antipyretic drugs.

INTRODUCTION:

Fever is a medical sign characterized by elevated body temperature above normal (36.5–37.5 °C /98–100 °F) due to an increase in temperature regulatory set point. It is a way of dissipating heat from the body to help regulate body temperature¹.

TYPES:

Performance of the various types of fever

- Fever continues
- Fever continues to abrupt onset and remission
- Fever remittent
- Intermittent fever
- Undulant fever
- Relapsing fever

The pattern of temperature changes may occasionally hint at the diagnosis:

Continuous fever:

Temperature remains above normal throughout the day and does not fluctuate more than 1 °C in 24 hours, e.g., lobar pneumonia, typhoid, urinary tract infection, brucellosis, or typhus.

Intermittent fever:

The temperature elevation is present only for a certain period, later cycling back to normal, e.g. malaria or septicemia.

Following are its types

- Quotidian fever, with a periodicity of 24 hours, typical of *Plasmodium falciparum* or *Plasmodium knowlesi* malaria.
- Tertian fever (48-hour periodicity), typical of *Plasmodium vivax* or *Plasmodium ovale* malaria.
- Quartan fever (72-hour periodicity), typical of *Plasmodium malariae* malaria.

Remittent fever:

Temperature remains above normal throughout the day and fluctuates more than 1 °C in 24 hours, e.g., infective endocarditis.

Pel-Ebstein fever:

A specific kind of fever associated with Hodgkin's lymphoma, being high for one week and low for the next week and so on.

A **neutropenic fever**, also called febrile neutropenia, is a fever in the absence of normal immune system function. Because of the lack of infection-fighting neutrophils, a bacterial infection can spread rapidly.

Febricula is an old term for a low-grade fever, especially if the cause is unknown, no other symptoms are present, and the patient recovers fully in less than a week².

BENEFICIAL EFFECTS:

In theory, fever can aid in host defense. There are certainly some important immunological reactions that are speeded up by temperature.

Research has demonstrated that fever assists the healing process in several important ways:

- Increased mobility of leukocytes
- Enhanced leukocytes phagocytosis
- Endotoxin effects decreased
- Increased proliferation of T cells⁴

PHYSIOLOGY OF THERMOREGULATION:

Body maintains constant temperature when heat production equals heat loss. This homeostasis of body temperature is maintained by hypothalamic thermostat. A center for control mechanisms of heat production and heat loss is present in the pre-optic area of hypothalamus. This receives input signals from Thermoreceptors^{5,6}.

Types of Thermoreceptors:

Thermoreceptors can be classified into:

- Peripheral Thermoreceptors (present in skin and mucous membranes)
- Central Thermoreceptors (present in internal structures such as hypothalamus).

Maintenance of normal body temperature by pre-optic area of hypothalamus (which acts as thermostat) occurs due to either increase or decrease in the firing of nerve impulses with increased and decreased temperature respectively. Hypothalamus contains heat-losing center (predominantly innervated by parasympathetic system) and heat-promoting center (predominantly innervated by sympathetic system)^{7,15}.

MECHANISMS OF HEAT PRODUCTION⁵:

Different mechanisms of heat production in body include:

Vasoconstriction: Vasoconstriction occurs due to sympathetic nerve stimulation leading to decreased flow of warm blood from internal organs to skin. Hence this leads to increase in body temperature.

Sympathetic stimulation: Stimulation of sympathetic system leads to secretion of epinephrine and norepinephrine (NE) which increases the cellular metabolism. This leads to increased heat production by the process of chemical thermogenesis.

Skeletal muscles: Increase in the muscle tone of skeletal muscles causes shivering by a process of involuntary thermogenesis.

Thyroid hormones: Cold environment leads to increased secretion of TRH by hypothalamus which leads to increased TSH production by pituitary gland. This causes increased production of thyroid

hormones (T3 and T4) leading to increase in metabolic rate and return body temperature.

MECHANISMS OF HEAT LOSS⁵:

Heat loss through the body occurs by vasodilatation; decreased metabolic rate and shivering or by increased perspiration which usually occurs by stimulation of sweat glands.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF FEVER^{6,8}:

A substance which induces fever is called a "pyrogen". Pyrogens can be:

Endogenous pyrogens: These are internal in nature. These include cytokines such as interleukins-1,6,8; tumour necrosis factor- α , β ; interferons $-\alpha$, β . These are produced by phagocytic cells and are released into circulation. These then cross BBB enter the brain and bind with endothelial receptors leading to activation of arachidonic acid pathway, release of PGE2 and fever.

Exogenous pyrogens:

These are external in nature. These include lipopolysaccharides (LPS) which are usually the components of cell walls of bacteria.

These LPS bind to LPS binding site to form a complex which binds to CD14 receptors present on macrophages. This causes synthesis and release of endogenous cytokines like IL-1,6; TNF- α , β ; and in turn activation of arachidonic acid pathway, PGE2 release and fever production⁷.

MECHANISM OF FEVER PRODUCTION:

Pyrexia can be due to infectious toxins or immune responses. These trigger the release of cytokines IL-1, 6; TNF which either act on Thermoreceptors to produce PGE2 in hypothalamus or EP3 receptors in vasomotor center which are also acted upon by PGE2. This leads to stimulation of sympathetic nerves and increased heat

Production by thermogenesis or decreased heat loss by skin vasoconstriction. This leads to production of fever by decreased heat dissipation. The new set point in hypothalamus remains elevated until PGE2 is no longer present⁸.

ANTIPYRETIC THERAPY:**CLASSIFICATION OF ANTIPYRETIC DRUGS^{10,11}:**

- I. Salicylates: Ex: aspirin, diflunisal
- II. P-amino phenol derivatives: Ex: paracetamol
- III. Pyrazolon derivatives: Ex: phenylbutazone, oxyphenbutazone
- IV. Benzoxazocaine derivatives: Ex: piroxicam, meloxicam
- V. Propionic acid derivatives: Ex: ibuprofen, ketoprofen

VI. Selective COX-2 inhibitors: Ex: celecoxib, paracoxib

HOME REMEDIES FOR FEVER:

Physical cooling methods such as sponging with luke warm or cold water, drinking lots of fluids and water help in controlling fever by decreasing the body temperature¹⁰.

(Massachusetts Department of Public Health
Flu: What You Can Do – Caring for People at Home
Fever and the Flu
Fall 2007)

PRECLINICAL PERSPECTIVE:

Animal models for pyrexia are important biological tools to understand basic processes development of fever and validate strategies for clinical treatment. In general, animal models (with the exception of some transgenic and targeted gene deletions) attempt to

reflect human pyrexia¹³. Often practical issues, such as cost, availability, housing costs, and animal husbandry, dictate the choice of animal model.

MODELS TO INDUCE PYREXIA¹⁴:

IN RATS: Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia: The subcutaneous injection of Brewer's yeast suspension produces fever in rats. Then the animals are treated orally with standard drug and test compound. The maximum reduction in rectal temperatures is calculated between different groups.

IN RABBITS: Lipopolysaccharide induced pyrexia: Intravenous injection of lipopolysaccharides induces fever in rabbits. Test compound is given subcutaneously or orally and decrease in body temperature is compared before administration of the test compound, which is monitored for at least 3 hours.

Table-II: PREVIOUS WORK DONE ON PLANTS:

S. No.	PLANT NAME	FAMILY	PLANT PART USED	ANIMALS USED	METHOD OF EXTRACTION	SCREENING MODEL	P-VALUE	YEAR
1	Eugenol	Myrtaceae	Clove oil	Rabbits	Saline suspension	IL-1 induced fever	<0.01	Feng et al, 1987 ³⁹
2	Andrographis alata	Acanthaceae	Whole plant	Male wistar rats	Alcoholic extracts	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	S.Balu et al, 1993 ²⁰
3	Clerodendron serratum	Verbanaceae	Roots	Mice/rats/rabbits	Ethanollic extract	Method of brownlee	<0.05	N.Narayanan et al, 1999 ⁴¹
4	Premna herbaceae	Verbanaceae	Roots	Mice/rats/rabbits	Ethanollic extract	Method of brownlee in rabbits	<0.01	N.Narayanan et al, 2000 ⁴⁰
5	Mallotus peltatus	Euphorbiaceae	Leaves	Wistar rats	Methanollic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.001	D.Chatopadhyay et al, 2002 ⁴⁶
6	Pergularia extensa	Asclepediaceae	Leaves	Wistar rats	Ethanollic	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.001	Jalalpure et al, 2002 ³⁰
7	Tabernaemontana pandacaqui	Apocyanaceae	Stems	Sprague dawley rats	Ethanollic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	T.Taesotikul et al, 2003 ⁴⁵
8	Alstonia macrophylla	Apocyanaceae	Leaves	Wistar rats	Methanollic extraction	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.001	Debprasad chatopadhyay et al, 2005 ¹⁸
9	Moringa oleifera	Moringaceae	Seeds	Male wistar rats	Ethanollic, petroleum ether extracts	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.001	Hukkeri et al, 2006 ²⁸

10	Peperomia pellucida	Piperaceae	Leaves	Albino rabbits	Ethanollic extract	Boiled milk induced pyrexia	<0.05	Alam khan et al, 2007 ²⁹
11	Radix paeoniae	Paeonaceae	Roots	Wistar rats	Acetone extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	Sapna motwani et al, 2007 ³⁴
12	Taxus wallichiana	Taxaceae	Leaves	Wistar rats	Methanolic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	Muhammed nisar et al, 2008 ⁴⁴
13	Mollugo pentaphylla	Molluginaceae	Whole plant	Wistar rats	Methanolic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.01	Valarmathi et al, 2010 ²⁶
14	Momordica charantia	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit	Wistar rats	Ethanollic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.01	Roshan patel et al, 2010 ²⁷
15	Argyreia speciosa	Convolvulaceae	Roots	Rats	Hydro-alcoholic extract by percolation	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	Sandeep ahlawat et al, 2010 ¹⁷
16	Cuscuta reflexa	Cuscutaceae	Whole plant	Wistar rats	Aqueous and ethanollic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	Sanjib bhattacharya et al, 2010 ²³
17	Capparis zeylanica	Capparaceae	Whole plant	Wistar rats	Methanolic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.01	Ranjan pradhan et al, 2010
18	Quisqualis indica	Combretaceae	Leaves	Wistar rats	Methanolic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.01	Nitu singh et al, 2010 ³⁵
19	Azima tetraacantha	Salvadoraceae	Leaves	Swiss mice	Ethanollic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.01	Nargis begum et al, 2011 ²¹
20	Platyclusus orientalis	Cupressaceae	Leaves	Albino rabbits	Petroleum ether	Boiled milk induced pyrexia	<0.05	Amit jaiswal et al, 2011 ³¹
21	Ficus bengalensis	Moraceae	Leaves	Swiss rats	Ethanollic and aqueous	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	Sachdev yadav et al, 2011 ²⁴
22	Geniosporum prostratum	Lamiaceae	Bark	Male albino rats	Ethanollic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.01	Anil kumar et al, 2011 ²⁵
23	Amaranthus viridis	Amaranthaceae	Whole plant	Male swiss mice	Methanolic extracts	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	Ashok kumar et al, 2011 ¹⁹

24	Plumeria rubra	Apocyanaceae	Leaves	Albino rabbits	Ethanollic	Boiled milk induced pyrexia	<0.05	Vimlesh mishra et al, 2012 ³²
25	Pongamia pinnata	Fabaceae	Leaves	Male wistar rats	Methanolic	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.01	Anupriya pandey et al, 2012 ³³
26	Vitex negundo	Verbanaceae	Leaves	Male swiss rats	Alcoholic	PGE1 induced pyrexia	<0.05	Jayashree tirumalsetty et al, 2012 ³⁶
27	Ziziphus jujube	Rhamnaceae	Leaves	Wistar rats	Methanolic	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.001	Balakrishnan et al, 2012 ³⁷
28	Psidium guajava	Myrtaceae	Dried leaves	Male wistar rats	Ethanollic extract	Yeast induced hyperpyrexia	<0.05	B. V. Owoyele et al, 2012 ³⁸
29	Radix puerariae	Leguminosae	Roots	Sprague dawley rats	Isoflavanoid puerarin	LPS induced fever	<0.05	Xiu Juan Yao et al, 2012
30	Saraca acosa	Caesalpiniaceae	Seeds	Wistar rats	Acetone extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.01	Sasmal et al, 2012 ⁴²
31	Tecomaria capensis	Bignoniaceae	Leaves	Albino rats	Methanolic extract	Brewer's yeast induced pyrexia	<0.05	Neeraj kumar saini et al, 2012 ⁴³

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